

D2.1 Playbook to guide the set-up of Testing Grounds and the Co-design of Business Models

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Summary

In this deliverable, D2.1: Playbook to guide the set-up of testing grounds and the co-design of business model(s), a guide is provided for the TG-leads to support the set-up of testing grounds and the co-design of business models.

This playbook is relevant in specific for the following project partners: EV ILVO (Belgium), AU (Denmark), THUENEN (Germany), WR (The Netherlands), IRWiR PAN (Poland) and CONSULAI (Portugal), which are the lead partners responsible for the regional testing grounds.

This guide will support the testing ground-leads in selecting soil health cases, setting-up the testing ground and guiding the process of co-designing a soil health business models. It provides a common understanding on vocabulary and concepts. It provides a common structure – explaining the steps to take for setting-up the testing grounds and co-designing a business model- and it provides the tools that help to reflect, analyze, and co-create in order to further develop a business model. As such, it helps streamlining the processes up to the end of year 1 (before implementation).

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Acronyms and abbreviations

BM	Business Model
CoP	Community of Practice
FBC	Flourishing Business Canvas
MRV	Monitoring, reporting, verification
SHBM	Soil Health Business model
SES	Soil-based Ecosystem Services
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TG	Testing ground
WP	Work package

Project consortium

No.	Participant organisation name	Country
1	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KU Leuven)	BE
2	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek (EV ILVO)	BE
3	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)	NL
4	Wageningen University (WU)	NL
5	European Landowners' Organization (ELO)	BE
6	Consultoria Agroindustrial (CONSULAI)	PT
7	Aarhus Universitet (AU)	DK
8	KOIS Invest (KOIS)	BE
9	MR F&A Consult (MFRA)	BE
10	Instytut Rozwoju Wsi i Rolnictwa Polska Akademia Nauk (IrWiR PAN)	PL
11	Thuenen Institut (THUENEN)	DE
12	Udruzenje Eko-Inovacija na Balkanu (ABE)	RS
13	Institute Navarro de Tecnologias e Infraestructuras Agroalimentarias (INTIA)	ES
14	Lietuvos Misko ir Zemes Savininku Asociacija (FOAL)	LT

Overview of the SoilValues project

SoilValues: Enhancing Soil health through Values-based business models (HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL02-05)

Project duration: 1 January 2023 – 31 December 2026 (48 months)

Total project budget: € 4 999 922.50

EU Grant: € 4 999 922.50

Land managers combine man-made resources with natural resources to produce marketable products like food, feed, fiber and wood, but at the same time produce ecosystem services that are generally not marketed or compensated. However, land managers generally have little incentive to invest in healthy soils, as they cannot sufficiently capture the value generated by these ecosystem services. SoilValues aims to contribute to the conditions for developing successful soil health business models. These are models in which land managers make production decisions that result in higher levels of soil-based ecosystem services (SES) and in which they are paid for the non-marketed services they generate. In order for such business models to function, three important conditions need to be fulfilled: (1) the outcomes of SES need to be measured, thus requiring knowledge, indicators and models, (2) the data and information generated by these indicators and models need to be exchanged to facilitate monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV), and (3) all these activities should be governed by an appropriate institutional framework consisting of the necessary legislation, standards and incentive schemes. To enhance the conditions for developing successful soil health business models, SoilValues will: (1) provide a comprehensive assessment framework addressing all factors influencing the development of business models for investing in soil health, (2) establish 6 testing grounds across Europe to test and improve emerging and designing new soil health business models, (3) establish 12 communities of practice of land managers, value chain actors, investors and public authorities for soil health business models, (4) design a comprehensive toolbox of incentives and policy recommendations to facilitate soil health business models and (5) raise awareness and exchange knowledge for soil health business models. This work is structured along five distinct work packages (WPs) as indicated in Figure 1.

1 Introduction to the playbook

In this deliverable, *D2.1: Playbook to guide the set-up of testing grounds and the co-design of business model(s)*, a guide is provided for the TG-leads to support the set-up of TGs and the co-design of BMs. This report is divided into 5 chapters across which the playbook is described in detail. The playbook itself is added in Annex A. Following a short introduction of the purpose of the playbook in chapter 1, chapter 2 describes the role of the playbook within the SoilValues project, specifically as it relates to work package (WP) 2. In chapter 3 the purpose and structure of the playbook are discussed. Chapter 4 and 5 summarize the two building blocks of the playbook, namely 'Set-up of the Testing Ground' and 'Co-designing of the Business Model'. Finally, chapter 6 briefly touches upon the follow-up and learning process of the TGs.

1.1 Why develop a playbook?

SoilValues aims to contribute to the conditions for developing successful soil health business models (SHBM). One of the expected results is to establish 6 TGs across Europe to test and improve emerging and designing new SHBM. The latter refers to a participative process in which a thorough analysis is done of the context in which the business models (BMs) should thrive. To streamline these important steps the playbook gives guidance to all consortium partners that will lead the setup of a TG, such that an efficient approach is established within the project.

1.2 A playbook for whom?

SoilValues will develop TGs in 6 countries that are managed by the following project partners: EV ILVO (Belgium), AU (Denmark), THUENEN (Germany), WR (The Netherlands), IRWiR PAN (Poland) and CONSULAI (Portugal). Each lead partner will set up the regional TG. This playbook is specifically developed for the aforementioned partners. However, the playbook also supports the TG-leads to inform the relevant actors within the TGs about the co-design processes of a BM. As such, these guidelines are relevant for all SoilValues partners, whether or not they are involved in the TGs or only in setting-up CoPs, as the latter play a pivotal role in the up-scaling of the BMs.

2 Situating the playbook within SoilValues WP2

Land managers can be stimulated to take production decisions resulting in higher levels of SES if they are rewarded for the non-marketed services they generate. The aim of SoilValues is to **enhance the conditions** for developing successful SHBMs, thus ensuring that land managers' efforts are being rewarded in a sustainable way. The overall goals of WP2 is to set-up **six TGs** that will design, test and improve **emerging or new SHBMs**. These TGs correspond to real life circumstances and will be set-up across Europe, representing a **diversity of farming systems** in different pedoclimatic, socio-economic and governmental **contexts**. As mentioned above, the six TGs will be established in Belgium (BE), Germany (DE), Denmark (DK), The Netherlands (NL), Poland (PL) and Portugal (PT), with TG-leads having been identified among the consortium partners.

The final aim is to enhance the adoption of sustainable soil health practices in the six different contexts. The first tasks within WP2 in line with this aim are (1) to establish TGs through the selection of soil health cases and the engagement of directly involved actors and (2) to co-design a BM requiring a thorough analysis of the local context.

The TG-leads are responsible for the set-up of the TGs within their context. Furthermore, the TG-leads are responsible to initiate and guide a **process enabling the development of a successful SHBM within the TG**. The latter refers to the **co-design phase**. Note that the **engagement of the directly involved actors** (i.e., stakeholders) is perceived as a crucial condition for the success of the testing grounds and the co-design process. The c-design phase implies a **step-by-step approach** in which:

- A soil health case is selected and the directly involved actors are identified
- The process is conducted in such a way that **stakeholders actively participate and their perspectives are taken into account**. This will ensure ownership and will support awareness raising to a broader constituency as the stakeholders will convey the relevance of SHBMs to their constituencies
- The context is analyzed together with all relevant actors. This includes identifying (other) actors, their needs, potential added value of the business, barriers and levers, etc... to enable further development of the case into a SHBM. Specific attention is paid to new rewarding mechanisms so as to have a viable and SM

Figure 1. Clarification of the period and tasks of WP2 to which the playbook relates.

3 Purpose and structure of the playbook

3.1 Purpose of the playbook

- The playbook is a **guide to support** two key phases of the SoilValues project: (1) the set-up of the TGs and (2) the co-design of BM (**Error! Reference source not found.**).
- The set-up of the TGs and the Co-design of the BMs phases result in the **building blocks to shape** a SHBM; they are the stepping stones to implementing a (new) or emerging SHBM.
- As a lot of terms are being used which need to be unambiguously interpreted, the playbook provides a **common understanding** of the vocabulary & concepts in the project.
- Furthermore, it provides a **common structure** for consortium partners to work with and explains the **steps to take** in setting up the TGs.
- Finally, it **provides (draft) tools** that help to reflect, analyze, and co-create in order to further develop a BM.

3.2 Structure of the playbook

As the playbook refers to two important phases in the project, i.e., the set-up of TGs and the co-design of BMs, these form its two major blocks. Firstly, an “Introduction” links the playbook to the aims of the SoilValues project and situates the playbook within WP2. Following this, block 1 “Set-up of the Testing Grounds” and block 2 “Co-design of the Business Models” are described. Both blocks consist of different steps (described in more detail in chapters 4 and 5). Each step is firstly described by **general information**, providing information about the “What”, “Why”, “Outcome” and “Timing”, followed by a description of the **tool**. Tools however may be updated or added, based upon new insights.

After block 1 and 2 a timeline is provided which highlights the most important outcomes and events at project level linked to each block.

4 Introduction to block 1: set-up of the Testing Ground

4.1 What is block 1 about?

Block 1 deals with the set-up of the TG. It provides instructions and tools to better understand the potential of a case in a given context to (further) develop it into a successful BM. Additionally, it provides guidance to make a selection of cases at project level, taking the diversity and complementarity of cases in account. Finally, it helps partners to set-up the TGs. The playbook describes **three steps for this block**.

4.2 Structure of block 1: different steps

Step 1: Reflection on cases

Step 1 elicits the reflection on (a) preliminary case(s) by partners by means of a 'Form for Reflection'. This form assists the TG-leads to make an informed choice about which case(s) are preferentially included in the SoilValues project. Using 2 cases as examples, the playbook demonstrates how to complete the questions presented in the form.

The form can be found in the SoilValues SharePoint folder, through [this link](#). A communication was sent out on the 4th of April to the consortium partners with detailed instructions on how to fill in the form. The TG-leads are invited to indicate a maximum of 2 preferred case(s).

Step 2: Selection of cases

After each TG-lead has completed the form, a selection phase will take place at the level of the project. This step allows to compare the positionality of all cases and to debate on the **diversity and complementarity of all cases**. The expected outcome is a final selection (out) of (the preferred) cases. It is expected that at consortium level, only one case per TG-lead is withheld. This step includes an online workshop at project level. The indicative timing of the selection workshop is the end of May 2023.

Step 3: Kick-off of the testing ground

Once it is clear which cases will be the subject of SoilValues and the further development into a SHBM, the stakeholders (i.e., the directly involved actors in each case) will be mobilized. This step forms the kickstart of the co-design process (to be carried out after summer 2023).

5 Introduction to block 2: co-design of the Business Model

5.1 Using the Flourishing Business Canvas

Block 2 deals with the co-design of the BM. Before the actual implementation of the SHBM (from January 2024 onwards), the playbook provides instructions and tools for co-designing such a SHBM (September – December 2023). The second block of this playbook provides **instructions and tools** to accompany this co-design phase. The scope of block 2 does not include accompaniment of the TG-lead for the implementation period.

The different steps of this block and the tools referred to are inspired by the Flourishing Business Canvas (FBC) (source <https://flourishingbusiness.org/flourishing-business-canvas/>) (**Error! Reference source not found.**), a visual collaborative tool to design BMs that takes into account the interdependencies of BMs with economy, society and the environment.

The FBC is described as an upgrade of the widely used Business Model Canvas (Elkington and Upward 2016). The FBC consists of three contextual systems: the environment, society, and the economy; four perspectives: process, people, value, and outcomes; and sixteen building blocks with topics and questions to think critically about a BM. The responses to these sixteen questions are used to describe and design the BM elements. The FBC is a tool that can provide a more holistic visual expression of a shared understanding of the framework within which the firm or organization and its stakeholders co-create sustainable BMs (Upward and Davies 2018). The use of the FBC contributes to individual and shared learning about integrated business sustainability by taking into account the co-creation of value and the importance of all stakeholders' interests (Äyväri and Jyrämä 2017). In this sense the FBC can motivate groups of people to engage in broader and deeper conversations about the elements of a BM, creating trust and supporting creativity and innovation. **Because of the extensiveness and complexity of the tool, the boxes and language used have been simplified and adapted to the SoilValues aims.**

Figure 2. The Flourishing Business Canvas

5.2 Structure of block 2: different steps

The first steps of the co-design process (described in more detail below as step 4 and step 5) are performed with the newly formed TG; this involves the TG-lead and the actors who are directly involved in the selected case. As step 4 includes a more thorough analysis of all actors and their needs, this step may result in identifying additional stakeholders (actors that need to be, or are, directly involved in the case). Steps 6 up to 8 are thus performed with the fully developed TGs. Step 5 consists of a SWOT analysis which will already highlight important aspects of the pursued SHBM. The outcome of step 5 can provide input for the consequent steps 6-8 (which will possibly be performed with a larger group of stakeholders).

Step 4: Actor and needs analysis

Step 4 consists of mapping and analysis of **all actors** who may have an interest in SHBM as well as **their needs** that explain that interest.

Step 5: SWOT analysis

Step 5 consist of a SWOT analysis. This method is used to identify and analyse internal **strengths** and **weaknesses** and external **opportunities** and **threats** of the pursued SHBM.

Step 6 – 8: Value, Process and Outcomes analysis

Steps 6 to 8 assist the participative process of reflecting upon the different components of a BM with all relevant stakeholders. This includes reflecting and analysing the services, products, and value

provided by the SHBM as well as reflecting and analysing the activities, involved resources and governance of the SHBM and the envisaged goals, as well as benefits and costs of the SHBM.

Block 2 will assist the TGs to have a clear view (by the end of December 2023) **regarding the final common purpose of developing a SHBM and how to achieve this**. This will result in an implementation plan and a completed business canvas (D2.2, WUR), and will serve as the starting point for the implementation phase (T2.4, KU Leuven).

6 Follow-up and learning process

The follow-up and monitoring is an inherent part of WP2 and includes closely tracking the performance of the TGs. This is foreseen through regular meetings with the TG-leads to follow up on the progress of setting-up TGs and co-designing BMs. Furthermore, WP2 and specifically task 2.1 will foster synergetic effects by organizing bi-annual meetings across TGs. Exchange across TGs will allow to share experiences, inspire each other and learn from the process in case of difficulties.

The follow-up and learning process is, however, not part of the playbook deliverable and will be described in a separate document.

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Appendix A: Playbook

Playbook

to guide the Set-up of Testing Grounds
and the Co-design of Business Models

ILVO

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Version 6 April 2023

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STEP 5: SWOT analysis

STEP 6: Value analysis

STEP 7: Process analysis

STEP 8: Outcomes analysis

Introduction

Situating the playbook within SoilValues (WP2) aims

- **Land managers** generally have little incentive to invest in healthy soils as they cannot sufficiently capture the value generated by the delivered ecosystem services. They **can be stimulated to take production decisions** - resulting in **higher levels of soil-based ecosystem services (SES)** - **if they are rewarded** for the non-marketed services they generate.
- The **aim of SoilValues** is to **enhance the conditions for developing successful soil health business models (SHBMs)**, thus ensuring that land managers' efforts are being rewarded in a sustainable way (economically viable, socially and environmentally just).
- Therefore, **six testing grounds will be set-up** across Europe, representing a **diversity of farming systems** in **different** pedoclimatic, socio-economic and governmental **contexts**. These testing grounds (TGs) correspond to real life circumstances and are ideal to design, test and improve (new) SHBMs.
- The six testing grounds will be established in countries BE, DE, DK, NL, PL and PT, where consortium partners have been indicated as the **TG-leads**.

Situating the playbook within SoilValues (WP2) aims

- The **TG-leads** are responsible for setting-up the TGs. Note that the **engagement of the direct involved actors** (i.e., stakeholders) is being perceived as a crucial condition for the further process
- Furthermore, the TG-leads are responsible for initiating and guiding a **process to enable the development of a successful SHBM**. The latter is the **co-design phase**. This implies a **step-by-step approach** in which:
 - a **soil health case** is being selected and the **directly involved actors** are being identified
 - the process is conducted in such a way that **stakeholders actively participate and their perspectives are being taken in account**. This will ensure ownership and will support awareness raising to a broader constituency as the stakeholders will convey the relevance of SHMBs to their constituencies
 - together with all relevant actors the context is being analyzed i.e. identifying (other) actors, their needs, potential added value of the business, barriers and levers,... to enable further development of the case into a SHBM

The playbook is a guide to support TG leads in these processes.

SoilValues WP2: process overview

Purpose of the playbook

- The playbook is a **guide to support** two key phases of the SoilValues project: the Set-up of the TGs and the Co-design of BMs (year 1). These phases inform the **building blocks to shape** a SHBM and are the stepping stones towards implementing a (new) or emerging SHBM

- It provides a **common understanding** of the vocabulary & concepts in the project
- It provides a **common structure** to work with
- It explains the **steps to take**
- It **provides tools** that help to reflect, to analyse, to co-create

Vocabulary and concepts

- **Case:** an initiative in which a conducive context is being created to reward land managers taking soil health measures
- **Soil health business model (SHBM):** model in which land managers make production decisions resulting in higher levels of SES and that **creates the conditions** for these efforts to be economically, socially and environmentally viable
- **Soil-based ecosystem services (SES):** not only carbon sequestration, see [FAO scheme](#)
- **Testing Ground (TG):** case + directly involved actors with a vested interest (i.e., stakeholders)
- **Community of Practice (CoP):** broader set of actors that are influenced by and/or can influence/upscale the testing ground
- **Co-design:** a participatory approach to designing SHBM in which participants are treated as equal collaborators

Block 1

STEP 1: Reflection on cases

STEP 2: Selection of cases

STEP 3: Kick-off of the testing ground

Introduction to block 1

The first part of this playbook deals with the “Set-up of the testing ground”. It provides instructions and tools to better understand the potential of a case in a given context to (further) develop it into a successful BM. Furthermore, it provides guidance to make a selection of cases at project level, taking the diversity and complementarity of cases into account. Finally, it helps partners to set-up the TGs.

The playbook provides **three steps for this block:**

1. Reflection on cases
2. Selection of cases
3. Kick-off of the TG

Step 1: Reflection on cases

What?

Reflect on the position of the preliminary case(s) with the help of this playbook and the 'Form for reflection'

Why?

- Assists to reflect on the broader **context of each case** (why was a particular case chosen, what are the consequences of that choice...).
- Allows to compare the positionality of each case that will allow a debate on the **diversity and complementarity of all cases at project level**.
- Helps partners that opt for a scoping phase in which several cases are still being considered **to analyze these and to make an informed choice**. In this approach, the guiding questions can be answered for each of the different cases under consideration.
- Helps to understand **which stakeholders should definitely be involved** in the case in order to set up a TG.

Outcome?

Filled in form per case. An idea who are the (directly involved) actors in the TG. Indication by the TG lead which case(s) would preferentially be chosen and why?

Timing? Practicalities

All partners submit the completed form for all cases considered by **30 April 2023**

The form is available through this link ['Form for reflection'](#)

A communication has been sent out to the SoilValues partners with additional information

Step 1: Reflection on case(s)

OVERALL INFO

1. What is the **name** of the case?
2. What is the **purpose(s)**
3. Which particular **soil care practice(s)** is (are) pursued or supported by the case?
4. To what extent is the case already **operational**? How mature is the case?
5. What are the **geographical characteristics** of the case (scale, operating area, soil type, climate, agricultural region...)?

ACTORS

6. **Who initiated** the case?
7. Which actors are already **involved** in the case?
8. In what way(s) are **farmers** involved?

VALUE

9. **Who** is (will be) **paid/rewarded** by the (imagined) BM (e.g. farmers, MRV services, are there any non-paid involvements...)?
10. **What resources** are mobilised by the case to enable the soil care practice (e.g. private money, loans, subsidies, access to land, infrastructure...)? By whom?
11. In what ways are the outcomes of the soil care practice already being **monitored**? Is there any historical soil data available on the case?
Can new soil data be expected during the SoilValues project?

Step 1: Reflection on cases

TOOLS

PROJECT LEVEL

12. Why is this case **relevant to** the SoilValues project as a whole (according to you, as a TG lead)
13. **‘Burning question’**: What is the **common purpose of the stakeholders** of further developing this case as a business model?
(see examples)

OVERALL INFO

Step 1: Reflection on case(s)

In this and subsequent slides, the purpose and type of response to the guiding questions are demonstrated using two imaginary examples A and B.

What is the **name** of the case?

- Case A: Carbon farming car fleet
- Case B: Local biodiversity cheese

What is the **purpose(s)** of the case?

- Case A: a municipality wants to offset emissions from its own car fleet and engages local farmers to achieve this
- Case B: dairy farmers get a premium price for taking soil and biodiversity measures on their farms thanks to the production and marketing of a local cheese for which consumers pay more

Which particular **soil care practice(s)** is (are) pursued or supported by the case?

- Case A: a range of carbon farming practices ('pick and choose' menu)
- Case B: a fixed set of soil and biodiversity measures

To what extent is the case already **operational**? How mature is the case?

- Case A: a pilot project had been running for a few years and a possible scale-up is currently being considered
- Case B: the idea exists but there is no concrete plan yet

What are the **geographical characteristics** of the case (scale, operating area, soil type, climate, agricultural region...)?

- Case A: local government, rich clay soils, moderate wet climate, family farms ~ 50 ha
- Case B: city region, sandy soils, moderate wet climate, dairy region, family farms ~ 75 ha

Step 1: Reflection on case(s)

In this and subsequent slides, the purpose and type of response to the guiding questions are demonstrated using two imaginary examples A and B.

Who initiated the case?

- Case A: local government wanting to offset carbon emissions from its own car fleet
- Case B: local cheesemaker looking for more locally produced organic milk

Which actors are already **involved** in the case?

- Case A: local government and 5 conventional farmers
- Case B: informal conversations between farmers, civil servant responsible for urban food policy, local cheesemaker and nature organisation

In what way(s) are **farmers** involved?

- Case A: some farmers are involved in a project set-up by a local government
- Case B: collaboration of farmers interested in transitioning and local cheesemaker

Step 1: Reflection on case(s)

In this and subsequent slides, the purpose and type of response to the guiding questions are demonstrated using two imaginary examples A and B.

Who is (will be) **paid/rewarded** by the (imagined) BM (e.g. farmers, MRV services, are there any non-paid involvements...)?

- Case A: only the farmers are rewarded, other stakeholders are civil servants with a fixed salary, MRV is very minimal and thus does not come with an external cost
- Case B: farmers are paid a better milk price, revenue model must also make sense for the local cheesemaker, and MRV is provided by nature conservation organisation with project funds (temporary basis)

What resources are mobilised by the case to enable the soil care practice (e.g. private money, loans, subsidies, access to land, infrastructure...)?

By whom?

- Case A: farmers have less costs as they have access to additional land; the land is public land owned by the municipality
- Case B: farmers are paid through better price (cash), society mobilises its members to buy this cheese (network), a local cheesemaker provides small-scale infrastructure crucial for processing the milk

In what ways are the outcomes of the soil care practice already being **monitored**? Is there any historical soil data available on the case? Can new soil data be expected during the SV project?

- Case A: municipality has made theoretical estimates of emission savings but does not actively measure them (activity-based instead of result-based) and does not plan to do so in the near future
- Case B: the project does not yet exist, so no data is available on impact yet

PROJECT LEVEL

Step 1: Reflection on case(s)

In this and subsequent slides, the purpose and type of response to the guiding questions are demonstrated using two imaginary examples A and B.

Why is this case **relevant to** the SoilValues project as a whole (according to you, as a TG lead)

- Case A: it opens the perspective on rewarding mechanisms including access to land which is an important challenge for farmers
- Case B: strong engagement of different local actors who have a complementary role in this new initiative

‘Burning question’: What is the **common purpose of the stakeholders** of further developing this case as a business model?

- Case A: to scale-up the case, involving more farmers; to assess whether the activity-based scheme is appropriate or whether a result-based scheme would be feasible in terms of costs-benefits
- Case B: to put the case into practice, an implementation plan is needed

TOOLS

Step 2: Selection of cases

What?

After each TG lead has completed the form and indicated which case(s) would preferentially be subject of SoilValues and why, this will be discussed at project level. A workshop with the involved partners will be held to select the cases to continue in the project.

Why?

- To have a diversity of cases project wide
- To ensure it is a feasible case: are the involved actors sufficiently engaged and motivated
- To ensure the cases are sufficiently innovative
- To ensure the relevance to the SoilValues project i.e. can we as a consortium elaborate sufficiently on our research questions

Outcome?

Six (or more) selected cases that become testing grounds

Time? Practicalities

End of May. A pre-meeting will be planned with the TG leads in order to prepare the workshop.

Step 3: Kick-off of the testing ground

What?

The aim of Step 3 is to mobilize the stakeholders (= actors directly involved) in the selected case. This step is the kickstart of the co-design process in each country. With these stakeholders, a full actor analysis will be done (Step 4) and a SWOT analysis (Step 5) from Sept. 2023 onwards. Thus, stakeholders should be informed and committed to do so. While kick-starting the TG, four elements should be addressed: a recap of the SoilValues project clarifying ambitions, a discussion on the selected case, a presentation of the outlines of block 2 and practical arrangements. A milestone (M2.1) of the project is the "Set-up of the testing ground".

Why?

- To mobilise the stakeholders
- To have a **common understanding of what the selected case is about and what the 'burning question' is according to (different) stakeholders?**
- To understand the next steps in the process related to the co-design of the BM (block 2, steps 4 -8)
- To prepare a schedule to ensure a smooth start of the process from Aug. - Sept. 2023 onwards

Outcome?

Start-up of the TGs + report of the meeting

Time?

By mid June 2023

Timing block 1

T2.2 Set-up TG

Block 2: Co-design of BM

STEP 4: Actor and needs analysis

STEP 5: SWOT analysis

STEP 6: Value analysis

STEP 7: Process analysis

STEP 8: Outcomes analysis

Introduction to block 2

Before the actual implementation of the SHBM (from January 2024 onwards), the phase of co-designing such a SHBM will take place (September – December 2023). The second block of this playbook provides **instructions and tools** to accompany this co-design phase.

The playbook provides **five steps**:

4. Actor and needs analysis
5. SWOT analysis
6. Value analysis
7. Process analysis
8. Outcomes analysis

Background information: The different steps of this second block and the tools they provide are inspired by a BM called “Flourishing Business Canvas”. The playbook provides a more straightforward version of this model and uses language and examples more relevant to the SHBM central to the SoilValues project. Partners looking for more detailed information on the Flourishing Business Canvas can find this [here](#) (Flourishing Business Canvas Website) and [here](#) (video impression of what it means to use the Flourishing Business Canvas).

Process overview Block 2

Step 4: Actor and needs analysis

What?

Mapping and analysis of **all actors** who may have an interest in SHBM as well as **their needs** that explain that interest. This includes both **directly involved actors with a vested interest (i.e., stakeholders)** as well as **indirectly involved actors**. In addition to actors who are likely to be positively affected by SHBM, actors who are likely to be negatively affected by SHBM are also considered.

Why?

A thorough analysis of all relevant actors and their needs is an important complement to the preliminary and probably incomplete composition of the TG (Step 3). After completion of Step 4, the composition of the TG can be adjusted if appropriate.

Outcome?

A good overview of all actors who have a relevant relationship with the SHBM and the needs that explain these relationships. A well-considered revisit of which actors will be involved in the TG (and the CoP in a later phase). All relevant actors should become stakeholders.

Timing?

September - October 2023

Step 5 can be carried out in parallel to step 4

Step 4: Actor and needs analysis

TOOLS

Step 4: Actor and needs analysis

A: Stakeholder identification

Make a list of all relevant actors. Do not use personal names for reasons of privacy.

Guiding questions

- **Beneficiary actors:** Who will/may benefit from the SHBM? Who will/may benefit from the soil ecosystem improvement delivered by the SHBM?
- **Owners-actors:** Which actors own the resources that will play an important role in the SHBM (e.g. land, nutrients, machinery, MRV systems, data...).
- **Antagonist actors:** Which actors that are not involved may (unintentionally) be affected, impacted or harmed by the SHBM? For less powerful actors, who is representing their needs; who is their more powerful voice/spokesperson?
- **Influencing actors:** Who will or may have a positive or negative influence on the context on which the success of the SHBM will rely (legislation, financial incentives, advice...).
- **Other actors?**

Step 4: Actor and needs analysis

B: Actors' needs and power-interest

Complete the following questions for each identified actor:

- **Benefits** from implementation of the SHBM (yes/no/maybe and why)
- **Motivation** for participating in the SHBM (and the TG)
- **Resources/power** that the actor possess and that could impact the SHBM (financial, knowledge, function, legitimacy, mobilisation...)
- **Overall needs** of the actor relevant for understanding its position towards the SHBM. Do not limit this exercise to financial needs (e.g. fair price for efforts made) but also consider utilitarian needs (e.g. something saves or costs extra time), autonomy issues (e.g. something enhances or constrains actors' freedom), psychological needs and positionality (e.g. believing or not believing in a certain kind of development)...

Power Interest grid (Eden & Ackerman, 1998, p. 122)

Background information on the Power Interest Grid: Stakeholders in the upper two categories are those with most stake (i.e., most 'interest') in the SHBM, but with varying degrees of power: those to the right-hand side enjoy more power to affect the SHBM's strategies, (i.e. they have 'influence') but may or may not actually be concerned about its activities. Thus 'Players' are those interested stakeholders who also have a high degree of power to support (or to sabotage) SHBM's strategies, whereas 'Subjects', while interested, have less influence. The two lower categories can perhaps be seen more as 'potential' stakeholders, who have not (yet) displayed much interest in the SHBM. 'Context setters' may have a high degree of power over the future of the SHBM, particularly in terms of influencing the future context within which its strategies will need to operate, while the last quadrant, the 'Crowd', (currently) exhibit neither interest in or power to influence strategy outcomes. (Based on source)

Step 4: Actor and needs analysis

C: Investigation of relationships between actors

TOOLS

Reflect on the relationship of each actor with all other actors. Use the following elements to characterize each relationship:

- Similar interests that make cooperation highly likely (e.g. share same concern towards the SHBM)
- Complementary interests that make cooperation highly likely (e.g. one needs MRV systems and other is able to deliver this service, i.e. commercial relationship)
- Opposing interests that will challenge cooperation within the SHBM (e.g. limited financial resources are to be divided between MRV service and farmer payment)
- (un)equal power relationship (e.g. one actor has long-term obligations towards the other) - Also, consider how power in a relationship may change over time, e.g. when a stakeholder becomes more reliant or dependent on the SHBM (e.g. farmers on SHBM for making a living, policy makers on SHBM for reaching policy goals...).

Summarise the most important relationships or observations that:

- May help promoting the creation of coalition between actors
- May help managing risks between stakeholders with strained relationships

Step 5: SWOT analysis

What?

Method for identifying and analyzing internal **strengths** and **weaknesses** and external **opportunities** and **threats** of the pursued SHBM.

Why?

Producing a SWOT analysis with the actors initially involved in the TG (Step 3) is a substantively important addition to the actor and needs analysis (Step 4). The outcomes of Step 4 and 5 will be used to review the composition of the TG before launching subsequent steps for co-designing the SHBM (Step 6-8).

Outcome?

SWOT-analysis

Timing?

September - October 2023

Step 5 can be carried out in parallel to step 4

Step 5: SWOT analysis

- Example of a strength: milk farmers delivering soil health efforts are able to charge a premium price for their efforts by processing the milk into a “soil health cheese” and marketing larger volumes of milk than would be the case if the milk were marketed
- Example of a weakness: the number of interested farmers exceeds the initial demand, potentially creating tension between partners
- Example of an opportunity: nature management organizations have acquired a large number of permanent grasslands in the region and are seeking partnerships with farmers for the management
- Example of a threat: the plans for the “soil health cheese” are met not only with enthusiastic reactions but also with very critical responses from vegan organisations

Note that strengths and weaknesses refer to **internal** factors, and opportunities and threats to **external** factors.

Process overview Block 2

Step 6: Value analysis

What?

Analysis of the services or products provided through a SHBM and the value created through the SHBM.

Why?

Value creation goes wider than mere financial payments. With this value analysis, we shed light on different types of value creation and consider the possibility that value may also be destroyed.

Outcome?

Completed form for reflection on the value derived from the SHBM.

Timing?

November – December 2023

Step 6 can be carried out in parallel to step 7 and 8

Step 6: Value analysis

Reflect on services, products and value provided by the SHBM

- Describe the services and/or products that are part of the SHBM. Which needs of which stakeholders are they supposed to meet?
- What value does each stakeholder derive from the SHBM? Is it a financial value (e.g. payment), a utilitarian value (e.g. access to land), a strategic value (e.g. control over decisions), a psychological value (e.g. be part of something)...? Consider that stakeholders can derive multiple values from the SHBM.
- Does the SHBM, alongside effects that meet certain needs of certain stakeholders, also have effects that conflict with other needs of these stakeholders (e.g. a financial reward for soil ecosystem services may come with increased administrative obligations a farmer might actually seek to reduce)?
- Is there a balance in the value stakeholders derive from SHBM or do some stakeholders derive much more value than others (e.g. for some it is a secondary income while for others it is the main income)?
- How might the value stakeholders derive from the SHBM evolve over time and what would this mean for their commitment to the SHBM (e.g. do the financial rewards that initially motivate farmers outweigh the obligations they will also have towards the SHBM such as MRV obligations)?

Step 7: Process analysis

What?

Analysis of some process related aspects of a SHBM: activities, resource use and governance.

Why?

The process analysis invites to consider not only which actors are involved in an SHBM, what needs they have and the extent to which these are met, but also the activities that the SHBM initiates and the process that is travelled through time.

Outcome?

Completed form for reflection on the process related aspects of the SHBM.

Timing?

November – December 2023

Step 7 can be carried out in parallel to step 6 and 8

Step 7: Process analysis

Reflect on the activities, involved resources and governance of the SHBM

- What activities are carried out by each stakeholder of the SHBM? Which activities create/deliver each product/service, create value and destroy value (use the outcomes of Step 6)?
- What tangible resources does your SHBM require or currently utilise? Are some resources obtained via privileged access (e.g. the SHBM grants access to publicly owned farmland not available to other actors outside the SHBM)?
- Is the SHBM taking a fair share of these resources, and is anyone or anything harmed in using these resources? How are decisions made about the ins and outs of the SHBM? E.g. single decision maker, multiple decision makers, unilateral, negotiated, consultative, majority, cooperative, or consensus?
- Which Stakeholders have the knowledge, information and power to make decisions about:
 - which actors are to be considered legitimate stakeholders of the SHBM?
 - the goals of the SHBM and how outcomes will be measured?
 - what the SHBM does now and in the future, the value it seeks to produce and the value destruction it seeks to avoid?
 - to what extent each stakeholder can participate in the decision-making process?

Please pay special attention to the position of farmers involved in the SHBM.

Step 8: Outcomes analysis

What?

Reflection on the expected outcomes of the SHBM and on how the actual outcomes will be monitored and discussed.

Why?

Underlying each SHBM are certain initial objectives. In this step, at the end of the co-design phase and before the start of the implementation phase, these initial objectives are thoroughly revisited. All the previously completed steps may prompt fine-tuning, critical reflection and adjustment where necessary.

Outcome?

Completed form for reflection on the outcomes of the SHBM.

Timing?

November – December 2023

Step 8 can be carried out in parallel to step 6 and 7

Step 8: Outcomes analysis

Reflect on the goals, benefits and costs of the SHBM

- What social, environmental and economic goals is the SHBM pursuing by the end of the SoilValues project and by other future milestones?
- What is the SHBM's definition of success: environmentally, socially and economically?
- How will the SHBM monitor and measure the benefits it produces? Which indicators are used? Please consider benefits that are both easy and hard to monitor and measure (e.g. non-monetised benefits).
- What are the social, environmental and economic costs of SHBM? E.g. founder's time, unpaid labour, paid experts and advisors, data management and platforms, communication, increased water consumption...
- How does this SHBM know if it is moving away from achieving its goals?

Timing block 2

The End

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